

COMPRESSION CREEP OF PULTRUDED ANGLE SECTIONS

Ghyslaine McClure and Yaghoub Mohammadi
Department of Civil Engineering and Applied Mechanics,
McGill University, Montréal, Québec, Canada H3A 2K6

ABSTRACT

An experimental investigation of the compression creep behaviour of pultruded angle stubs made of isophthalic polyester resin reinforced with an E-glass fiberglass mat of 35-45 % weight was conducted. Coupon creep tests were carried out in parallel with the stub tests, and results of the two series of tests are compared in view of validating the use of coupon test results for predicting creep deformations of full-sized members. The total duration of the tests was 2 500 hours in creep followed by 250 hours in creep recovery. Results indicate a scatter in the order of $\pm 15\%$ in creep strain measurements after 2 500 hours, for both stub and coupon tests. Predictions using Findley's power law with creep parameters determined from stub tests and coupon tests are in excellent agreement, both with one another and with actual creep strain measurements on the stubs.

Keywords: compression creep, pultruded shapes, glass fibre reinforced plastic, laboratory measurements

1. INTRODUCTION

Antenna-supporting structures are interesting applications for pultruded composite shapes. Electromagnetic transparency is an important advantage in lattice supports of FM and multi-directional antennas, whose radiation pattern is disturbed by the presence of metallic obstacles. Especially in structures operating in cold regions where ice and snow loads amplify wind effects, large loads can prevail for relatively long durations, ranging from a few days to several months, and creep investigations become necessary if pultruded glass fibre reinforced plastics (GFRP) are to be considered as alternatives to traditional structural materials. Furthermore, geometrical integrity of telecommunication structures is crucial for reliable serviceability.

Coupon testing procedures are becoming available to determine creep characteristics of GFRP, but very few investigations have been done on full scale structural elements or complete structures made of commercially produced pultruded shapes. As a result, the question of extrapolation of coupon creep data to larger elements remains problematic, especially in view of the variability of the properties measured in low-cost mass produced pultruded shapes.

Among the few recent experimental results reported, one should acknowledge the work of Mosallam

and Bank (1991, 1990), on a full-sized portal frame made of wide flange pultruded glass/vinylester sections. Their work dealt with tensile and shearing creep strain measurements, and they have concluded that creep parameters obtained from coupon tests can be used to describe the creep behaviour of FRP structures. The small number of points of strain measurements considered on the structure (a total of 20 for the entire structure), however, makes it difficult to assess the variability of the results in relation to acceptable levels of variability for design purposes.

In this study, compression creep measurements are made on coupons and on centrally loaded angle stubs, in an effort to assess the variability of creep parameters obtained from coupon tests and angle stub tests. Findley's theoretical creep model (Findley 1960) is used throughout for comparisons and predictions of creep deformations on full-sized members. Creep parameters defined in Findley's model are presented in Section 3. Observations indicate a large scatter in total strain measurements, due to non-homogeneous material properties of the stub angles and resulting eccentricities between the centroid and the centre of rigidity, but a relatively homogeneous creep behaviour.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Tests Specimens

The material used is an isophthalic polyester resin reinforced with a fiberglass mat of E-glass fibres for a nominal proportion of 35-45% in weight. It was supplied by Technical Pultrusion Inc., a local Québec manufacturer. The longitudinal modulus of elasticity was rated 15 840 MPa (2.3×10^6 psi) in uniaxial tension and compression. The stub dimensions were of 50,8 mm x 50,8 mm x 6,3 mm (2 in. x 2 in. x 1/4 in.) and their length was 305 mm (6 in.).

The tensile coupons, used for experimental confirmation of the tensile longitudinal modulus of elasticity, were of dimensions 12,70 mm x 6,35 mm (1/2 in. x 1/4 in.) with 50,8 mm (2 in.) gauge length and had a dumbbell shape in accordance with ASTM Standard D638-89 Type 1. The compression coupons were cut in a prismatic shape according to ASTM Standard D695-89 with the same cross-section as for the tension coupons and a length of 31,75 mm (1.15 in.) resulting in an effective slenderness ratio in the order of 12, since end conditions are nearly fixed with the creep fixture used.

2.2 Characterization of Primary Mechanical Properties

Destructive tests were conducted on twelve coupons in compression and eight in tension and stress-strain relationships were measured. Coupons coming from different angle legs were distinguished since preliminary tests had shown that one leg was stiffer and stronger than the other. After discussion with the manufacturer, it was concluded that this asymmetric behaviour was due to positioning of the mold during the pultrusion process itself.

All tests were performed in the Jamieson Structures Laboratory of McGill University, Canada, using an Instron machine, model No. KRD-212-260, at jaw speed of 1,27 mm (0.05 inch) per minute. All coupon specimens were instrumented with two strain gauges to measure longitudinal strains on both surfaces.

Coupon tests results are summarized in Table 1 where it is observed that coupons from Leg 1 were in the order of 40% stiffer and 50% stronger than those from Leg 2. The average value of the modulus of elasticity of coupons cut from Leg 2 in tension is 1,1% below the nominal value guaranteed by the manufacturer, and 2,7% above nominal in compression. Stress-strain curves

obtained were linear in all tests at strain levels above 1 000 microdeformations.

Table 1. Averages⁽¹⁾ of measured longitudinal mechanical properties of coupons

Property	Unit	Leg No.	Tension Test	Compression Tests
Modulus of Elasticity	GPa	1	22,3 ± 3%	21,9 ± 5%
		2	15,7 ± 2%	16,3 ± 4%
Ultimate Stress	MPa	1	255 ± 8%	313 ± 3%
		2	162 ± 7%	207 ± 6%
Ultimate Strain	10 ⁻³	1	11,2 ± 2%	14,3 ± 11%
		2	10,7 ± 2%	12,8 ± 11%

⁽¹⁾ Averages of four results for tension and six results for compression.

Compression-crushing tests were also conducted on angle stubs in order to determine the safe stress level to use later in the creep tests. The ends of the stubs were restrained by a 17,5 mm (11/16 in.) thick wooden plate snugly fit to the angle section and glued to a 25,4 mm (1 in.) thick steel plate, as illustrated on Fig. 1. This condition, while not perfectly fixed, provided sufficient restraint considering the centric compression load to be applied in the creep tests. As expected, failure systematically occurred by buckling of the weakest leg, at an average stress of about 140 MPa, but strong nonlinearities started to appear at around 100 MPa. This last observation is of importance to determine the stress level for the creep tests, in order to avoid nonlinear effects due to constitutive properties, and a target value of 50 MPa was adopted.

2.3 Experimental Apparatus

2.3.1 Creep Test on Angle Stubs

The angle stub specimen of Fig. 1 is shown in a loaded position, in a lever arm apparatus loaded with dead weights at the free end. Three identical apparatuses were constructed with a lever arm of 1 600 mm that multiplies the applied dead load by a factor of 10. Load transfer is achieved by a ball bearing on the top steel plate, at the centroid of the angle section. Each cantilever arm system was precisely calibrated using a 0-22,25 kN load cell.

Selection of an appropriate strain gauging configuration was based on preliminary creep tests with three types of gauges (6 mm, 90 mm and 120 mm) and geometric layouts. The most reliable results were obtained using three 6 mm gauges (Type CEA-06-240UZ-120) per face for a total of twelve gauges per stub, and this configuration was retained for the formal 2 500-hour creep tests. This large number of measurements allows validation of the readings.

Figure 1 Compression Creep Set-Up for Angle Stub.

Figure 2 Compression Creep Fixture for Coupon.

2.3.2 Creep Test on Coupons

Three identical compression creep fixtures were also constructed for the coupons, and one is shown on the photograph of Fig. 2. This fixture is quite simple and was adapted from an original design by Irion (1980). It consists of four 50,8 mm x 50,8 mm x 38,10 mm (2 in. x 2 in. x 1 1/2 in.) blocks of steel, each with one face milled with a rectangular slot in order to receive the coupon. Two pairs of steel blocks are bolted together with two transverse rods, and vertical spacing and alignment is maintained by two 19 mm (3/4 in.) solid round rods. The fixture can accommodate coupons of various lengths and thicknesses. The coupon of Fig. 2 is shown in a loaded position, by a cantilever arm apparatus similar to those used for stub testing. A 6 mm strain gauge is used at the centre of each large face.

2.4 Preliminary Creep Tests on Angle Stubs

Three angle stubs were subjected to a 350 hour preliminary creep test (and 150 hours of creep recovery) in order to validate and finalize the design of the experimental set-ups and testing variables. The tests were conducted in July and August 1992.

The load level selected for the preliminary tests was relatively low (20% of the theoretical buckling load of the angle stub) but was increased in the formal tests to amplify creep effects. In addition to confirming the superior performance of the twelve-gauge set-up, these tests have shown the large variability ($\pm 20\%$) in the instantaneous strain measurements. Spatial variation of the modulus of elasticity on a given angle leg, inferior to $\pm 5\%$ according to the results of Table 1, cannot alone explain this result. A more important factor is the large difference in moduli obtained for the two legs, which cause eccentricities between the centroid of the section and its centre of rigidity. No attempt was made to compensate for these eccentricities, recognizing that they would be likely to occur in real truss structures also.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Creep of Angle Stubs

Formal 2 500 hour compression creep tests on three angle stubs were carried out from September 1992 to February 1993. The ambient temperature and degree of relative humidity were kept practically constant throughout the test (at 24°C and 25%, respectively) and readings on an unloaded reference specimen have indicated that no significant corrections were needed to account for environmental conditions.

Time histories of longitudinal strains are shown in Fig. 3 (a) and (b) for a total of 9 gauges of Leg 1 (strongest leg) of Stubs Nos. 1 and 2, respectively. Figs. 3 (c) and (d) show the corresponding graphs on a common logarithmic scale, where ϵ is the total strain measured at time t (in hours) and ϵ_0 is the initial instantaneous strain measured at time t_0 . Logarithmic graphs are close to straight lines - a best fit is shown for each set data set - and the creep parameters as defined by Findley (1960) are the slope, n , of the line and its intercept, m , at initial time:

$$\log (\epsilon - \epsilon_0) = m + n \log (t/t_0) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{or } \epsilon = \epsilon_0 + m (t/t_0)^n. \quad (2)$$

The average value of the initial instantaneous strain, ϵ_0 , is 2 000 microdeformations with a

coefficient of variation of 10%. This strain level represents only 14% of the ultimate strain measured

on coupons cut from Leg 1 (See Table 1) and corresponds to an average applied stress of 44 MPa. The average values of the creep parameters are of $78 \pm 30\%$ for m , and $0,17 \pm 6\%$ for n . Note that n is not affected by the intensity of the initial stress (or initial strain), which explains its low coefficient of variation. The parameter m , however, depends on the stress level. Findley (1960) has represented this stress dependency by a hyperbolic sine function and, taking $t_0 = 1$ hour, a more general form of (2) is

$$\epsilon = \epsilon_0' \sinh(\sigma/\sigma_0) + m' \sinh(\sigma/\sigma_0) t^n \tag{3}$$

where $\sigma_0 = \sigma_t$ (for this particular material) and is the stress corresponding to ϵ_0' , and σ is the initial stress level for which the total strain ϵ is to be determined. ϵ_0' and m' are known reference values.

Figure 3 Time histories of the total strain ϵ from creep tests on stubs (Leg 1).

3.2 Creep of Coupons

Two time histories of longitudinal strains are shown in Fig. 4 (a), corresponding to Coupon No. 2 cut from the angle strongest leg. Fig. 4 (b) represents the same results in logarithmic form. The average value of the initial instantaneous strain measured on the three coupons tested, ϵ_0 , is 6 700 microdeformations with a coefficient of variation of 3% only. This strain level represents 47% of the ultimate strain measured in compression (See Table 1) and corresponds to an average applied

stress of 147 MPa. The average values of the creep parameters are of $127 \pm 7,5\%$ for m , and $0,25 \pm 3\%$ for n . It is observed that all measurements on coupons present much less variability than those on stubs.

Figure 4 Time histories of the total strain ϵ from creep tests on Coupon 1 (cut from Leg 1)

3.3 Creep Predictions Using Coupon Properties

Predictions of creep strains in the stubs (Leg 1) using Findley's model can be done by using Equation (2) with the properties measured for the stubs, or with Equation (3) with the properties of the coupons. Results are summarized in Table 2 and compared with actual measurements at time $t = 2\,500$ hours. Minimum, average and maximum values are shown to emphasize the variability of the results. Firstly, it is observed that average predictions with coupon properties and stub properties are in excellent agreement with a difference inferior to 5%, and correspond to 15% of the initial strain. Secondly, the scatter on predictions with the stub properties ($\pm 35\%$) is more than twice that using coupon properties. This is an important finding from a designer point of view. Thirdly, predictions using Findley's model are also in excellent agreement with creep measurements on stub angles. The average creep strain measured on Leg 1 is of 320 microdeformations with a coefficient of variation of 16%. Lastly, in terms of variability of the results, Findley's model with coupon properties provides the best estimate of the scatter in actual measurements.

Table 2. Creep strain in stub after 2 500 hours.

	Findley's model with stub properties			Findley's model with coupon properties			Direct measurements on stubs
	$m^{(2)}$	n	$\epsilon_{2500} - \epsilon_0^{(2)}$	m	n	$\epsilon_{2500} - \epsilon_0$	
Minimum	55,5	0,163	199	112,5	0,241	257	248
Average	78	0,172	300	127	0,254	313	320
Maximum	100,5	0,181	414	139,2	0,261	357	393

⁽²⁾ Units for m and ϵ are microdeformations.

4. CONCLUSION

An experimental investigation of compression creep in pultruded GFRP angle stubs has been reported. Test results for a total duration of 2 500 hours indicate that the best estimate of creep strains is obtained using Findley's creep model with parameters determined from coupon tests. Creep parameters determined directly from stub tests only introduce a larger scatter in the predictions.

Acknowledgements

The authors are thankful to the McGill Faculty of Graduate Studies and Research for its financial support. A scholarship from the Ministry of Culture and Higher Education of the Islamic Republic of Iran is also gratefully acknowledged by the second author.

References

- Mosallam, A.S., Bank, L.C. *Creep and Recovery of a Pultruded FRP Frame*, Advanced Composites Materials in Civil Engineering Structures, Proceedings of the Specialty Conference on Advanced Composites Materials in Civil Engineering, Las Vegas, Jan. 31-Feb.1 1991, ASCE, pp. 24-35.
- Bank, L.C., Mosallam, A.S. *Creep and Failure of a Full-Size Fiber Reinforced Plastic Pultruded Frame*, Composite Material Technology, ASME PD-Vol. 32, 1990, pp. 49-56.
- Findley, W.N., *Mechanism and Mechanics of Creep of Plastics*, SPE Journal, January 1960, pp. 57-65.
- ASTM Standard D638 *Test for Tensile Properties of Plastics*, Annual Book of ASTM Standards, Part 35.
- ASTM Standard D695 *Test for Compressive Properties of Rigid Plastics*, Annual Book of ASTM Standards, Part 35.
- Irion, M.N., *Compression Creep Testing of Composite Materials*, M.S. Thesis, Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Wyoming, May 1980, pp. 8-13.